

Network for phytosanitary
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EUPHRESKO III

Strengthening phytosanitary research programming and collaboration: from European to global phytosanitary research coordination

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2. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

APAARI: Asia-Pacific Association of Agricultural Research Institutions

CBS: Citrus Black Spot

EPPO: European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization

FR: France

GB: United Kingdom

GR: Greece

HLB: Huanglongbing

HTS: High-throughput sequencing

IE: Ireland

IT: Italy

JKI: Julius Kühn-Institut

LAC: Latin America and the Caribbean

NBAIR: National Bureau of Agricultural Insect Resources

NPPO(s): National Plant Protection Organization(s)

PoC: Point-of-Care

RDLN: Regional Diagnostic Laboratory Network

(RT-)PCR: (Reverse Transcriptase)-Polymerase Chain Reaction

ST: sequence types

ToBRFV: tomato brown rugose fruit virus

US: United States of America

3. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The research projects initiated through Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III are small to medium-sized projects commissioned to provide evidence on specific questions. The research projects are not necessarily intended to deliver break-through science and innovation but fall into the category of explorative and applied science needed to support policy (Giovani *et al.*, 2019). Thus, the research activities commissioned through the Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III joint calls will support regulatory aspects and, in particular, the activities of the National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs).

As policymakers are one of the target groups of Euphresco/EUPHRESKO III, factsheets for policymakers are published to provide recommendations from national and transnational research activities.

The first series of factsheets focusses on diagnostics. A general introduction on the topic is followed by the recommendations for each of the nine regions identified in the EUPHRESKO III project, namely: Africa, Australia, Central Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, North America, Northern Europe, the Pacific islands, South-East Asia, and Southern Europe and Mediterranean.

4. INTRODUCTION

Reliable and rapid diagnostic processes are essential to support inspection activities conducted by NPPOs in the framework of their official mandate, and to evaluate the efficacy of measures taken. Official controls aim to prevent or reduce the risk of introducing new pests through the agri-food trade and to protect consumer interests. The reliability and consistency of these controls contribute to effective trade. In this context, validated and internationally accepted measures are of the utmost importance, as they support the harmonisation of detection and identification procedures worldwide and contribute to greater transparency and comparability in the diagnosis of regulated pests (Giovani *et al.*, 2017).

This document compiles 9 factsheets for policymakers from the 9 regions of the EUPHRESKO III consortium: Africa, Australia, Central Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, North America, Northern Europe, the Pacific islands, South-East Asia, and Southern Europe and Mediterranean.

The pests covered are:

- Bacteriology: '*Candidatus Liberibacter americanus*', *Ralstonia solanacearum*, *Xanthomonas citri subsp. Citri*, *Xylella fastidiosa*.
- Entomology: *Bactrocera dorsalis*, *Diaphorina citri*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Tuta absoluta*
- Mycology: *Colletotrichum* spp., *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *ubense* Tropical Race 4 (*Foc* TR4), *Phyllosticta citricarpa*, *Phytophthora* spp.
- Nematology: *Meloidogyne* spp.
- Virology and Phytoplasmology: banana bunchy top virus (BBTV), tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), various plant viruses and viroids.

5. RESEARCH OVERVIEW

5.1 Africa

Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) is an important emerging and highly contagious tobamovirus that poses a significant threat to tomato and pepper production worldwide, including in Africa. It is present in Morocco and Egypt in tomatoes. The pest is listed as a Regulated Non-Quarantine Pest (RNQP) in the European Union. It is, therefore, a requirement to declare ToBRFV status by African countries exporting any of the listed hosts of ToBRFV to the European Union. Rapid and accurate testing methods remain important for testing of imported tomato and capsicum seeds that represent a significant entry pathway for the pest.

5.2 Australia

Xylella fastidiosa is the number one exotic national priority pest for Australia due to its broad host range and the significant threat it poses to agricultural and horticulture industries. In other parts of the world, including Europe and the United States, outbreaks of *X. fastidiosa* have caused significant crop losses and socio-economic impacts.

X. fastidiosa is transmitted by insect vectors and can infect over 700 plants. The symptoms caused by *X. fastidiosa* include leaf scorch, chlorosis and decline, and often resemble other disorders, such as water stress or nutrient deficiencies.

While Australia has not reported the presence of *X. fastidiosa*, the region continues to remain prepared by implementing diagnostics and surveillance research to ensure the capability and capacity is in place to respond to an incursion of the bacterium (Constable F, 2022).

5.3 Central Asia

Widespread in cotton-growing countries, *Helicoverpa armigera* (cotton bollworm) damages more than 120 plant species, causing particularly significant damage in Tajikistan, Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan. In agriculture, the management of the pest is carried out based on a system that combines biological methods. However, modern technologies for effective control of cotton bollworm have not yet been sufficiently introduced. Cotton bollworm causes significant damage to cotton crops. In Uzbekistan, 80% of the biological methods are used to protect cotton from pests. Climate change is occurring very rapidly in Central Asia. Pests and diseases quickly adapt to these conditions. There is no level of adaptation of pests to biological agents used to protect plants. Therefore, research is being conducted in collaboration with scientific organizations in Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia and Tajikistan on alternative means and methods of control. On average, 15-20% of all agricultural crops die under the influence of harmful organisms.

5.4 Latin America and the Caribbean

Early and accurate diagnosis of plant pests is a major challenge across Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). The region is increasingly exposed to invasive organisms such as *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *cubense* Tropical Race 4 (*Foc* TR4), *Spodoptera frugiperda*, *Diaphorina citri*, and *Tuta absoluta*, which threaten food security and agricultural exports. Yet, many countries

in the region still lack adequate capacity to detect these pests in a timely and coordinated manner.

Laboratories in several countries operate with limited infrastructure, outdated equipment or insufficiently trained personnel. Additionally, there is no regional system to harmonise diagnostic protocols or facilitate information exchange, which slows down responses and restricts regional cooperation. The EUPHRESKO III regional consultation highlighted these gaps and emphasised the need for rapid, affordable and standardised diagnostic tools, particularly those adaptable to field conditions. Countries across the region expressed strong interest in improving their diagnostic readiness through collaborative approaches.

5.5 North America

Viruses and viroids are important pathogens in agricultural and horticultural crops whose geographical spread is increasing through climate change and globalization of trade. These pathogens are primarily managed through quarantine, eradication measures and vector control. Availability of naturally resistant cultivars is limited. Traditional detection methods are either slow and imprecise or rely on prior knowledge of these pathogens.

High-throughput sequencing (HTS) offers a powerful alternative that is rapid and sensitive, enabling the detection of both known and unknown viruses without prior information. For HTS to be widely adopted in diagnostics for quarantine and export testing, standardized and validated workflows are essential.

A recent Euphresco project (Ziebell *et al.*, 2021) explored various sample preparation, sequencing and analysis methods to enhance HTS effectiveness in plant virus diagnostics.

5.6 Northern Europe

Invasive *Phytophthora* pathogens are causing significant economic damage to agricultural, horticultural and forestry crops worldwide, as well as ecological damage to native plant species in wider environments. *Phytophthora* spp. is well adapted to thriving in plant nurseries, particularly in water, soil and on plant roots. Since much of the *Phytophthora* life cycle takes place in these substrates, the diseases they cause are difficult to diagnose and control.

A recent project in the United Kingdom has developed and tested a metabarcoding method for the analysis of *Phytophthora* diversity in water and root samples from nurseries operating different management practices.

The sampling and metabarcoding detection methods can be used for early detection of *Phytophthora* in import/export nurseries and in traded plants.

5.7 Pacific Islands

X. fastidiosa has been detected in 712 plant species and has three subspecies (including *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *fastidiosa*, *multiplex* and *pauca*), which are further subdivided into sequence types (ST). In areas where *X. fastidiosa* has not been detected (e.g. Pacific Islands, Australia, New Zealand), there is a need to develop diagnostic approaches that provide information on novel *X. fastidiosa*–host plant relationships that inform policy in the form of border clearance, diagnostic selection, host plant risk assessment and incursion response. Enhanced international collaboration and coordination can underpin this policy development and this example reflects such a process in the Pacific region.

5.8 South-East Asia

South and Southeast Asia increasing agricultural productivity and trade volumes have been accompanied by a heightened threat of pest incursions, such as viral pathogens and invasive insect species like fruit flies. Despite the existence of NPPOs and diagnostic laboratories, there are notable challenges including lack of standardized protocols, limited technical expertise, inadequate infrastructure and insufficient cross-border coordination (De Silva *et al.*, 2019). These gaps hinder timely pest identification and response, leading to prolonged outbreaks, trade restrictions and economic losses.

These challenges can be smoothed by establishing a coordinated regional diagnostic framework. By linking national laboratories under a shared system, faster and harmonized diagnostics will be enabled, knowledge exchange promoted and sustainable technical capacity built.

5.9 Southern Europe and Mediterranean

Inspection of *Citrus* fruits at the border for the detection of citrus black spot (CBS) is mostly based on visual examination followed by laboratory testing of fruits exhibiting suspicious symptoms. However, due to the long incubation period of *Phyllosticta citricarpa*, CBS symptoms on fruits are visible only at maturity, several months after infection. Furthermore, symptoms are usually non-specific and could be confused with other diseases such as anthracnosis and alternariosis.

In Argentina and Brazil, countries where CBS is present, exporters perform an ethephon treatment to enhance symptom expression on fruits in order to avoid that asymptomatic CBS-infected fruits will be rejected upon arrival in Europe.

Such treatment can be envisaged to be used in CBS survey plans for fruits harvested in orchards as well as in imported fruits.

6. DISCUSSION/ANALYSIS OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

6.1 Africa

Current diagnostics tools are sufficient but the development of point of care diagnostic assays are needed. Plans are underway to provide seed money to support development of Point-of-Care (PoC) diagnostic assays for tomato brown rugose fruit virus.

6.2 Australia

In a large collaborative research project supported by Hort Innovation Australia, the National Diagnostic Protocol for *X. fastidiosa* was developed and validated to ensure that Australia is adopting the world's best practice methods. This enables the rapid and accurate detection of *X. fastidiosa* if it was introduced to Australia to facilitate a swift response.

The National Diagnostic Protocol includes a combination of extensively validated laboratory and field-based molecular assays, that were published by other international researchers or developed within the project, for the identification and differentiation of *X. fastidiosa* spp. to sequence type and for use during high throughput surveillance.

High throughput sequencing and rapid multilocus sequence typing methodologies were also developed, to enable accurate identification of *X. fastidiosa* species, subspecies and sequence type to inform surveillance strategies based on host specificity.

The Ministry of Primary Industries of New Zealand developed a collection of accurately characterised *X. fastidiosa* spp. isolates, and DNA was shared with the Australian project participants; this critical resource not only assisted the National Diagnostic Protocol development but will support future diagnosis and surveillance within Australia.

As well as developing state-of-the-art diagnostic tools, technologies and protocols to screen plant material entering the country and to support active surveillance programs, it provided associated training for technical staff in diagnostic laboratories.

6.3 Central Asia

The level of occurrence of cotton bollworm in cotton fields was determined. Biological control agents against cotton bollworm were used in the participating countries. *Trichogramma* spp. and *Habrobacon hebetor* were used, resulting in good levels of pest control.

6.4 Latin America and the Caribbean

A successful example of regional cooperation in diagnostics is 'Candidatus Liberibacter americanus', the Latin American HLB (citrus greening disease) diagnostic network. National institutions in Brazil, Mexico and Cuba joined efforts to create a shared protocol for PCR-based detection, coordinated early surveillance actions and provided technical training for plant health professionals across countries. This approach allowed quicker and more consistent detection of the disease and reduced the risk of its further spread. The experience demonstrated that pooling regional expertise and standardizing procedures can significantly improve phytosanitary preparedness.

Consultation participants also reported that diagnostic efforts in LAC are often fragmented and duplicated. Institutions tend to work in isolation, with limited access to validated tools or common methodologies. This leads to inefficiencies and delays in identifying and managing pest outbreaks. There is broad consensus that regional coordination should be strengthened through joint diagnostic initiatives, investment in mobile diagnostic teams and the creation of shared reference laboratories. Additionally, policy support is needed to facilitate the adoption of common diagnostic standards and ensure sustainable capacity building in the region.

6.5 North America

Participants shared their experiences with different protocols for enrichment of viral sequences in nucleic acid preparations, and Gaafar and Ziebell (2020) carried out a comparative study for RNA on a range of different viruses. Most participants used commercial kits or contracted facilities to create libraries for HTS. The exception were the Peruvian and Hungarian partners who worked together to compare their in-house methods to prepare libraries for IonTorrent sequencing

The comparison of sequencing platforms was investigated as part of the proficiency test and test performance studies with the assumption that sufficient sequencing depth to identify unknown viruses/viroids would be obtained by any of the sequencing systems used by the participants. Further information can be found in the paper by Visser *et al.* (2016).

Though many bioinformatics pipelines exist to analyse HTS, two specific to plants were identified: VirusDetect and VirTool. VirTool was chosen because it handled data from Illumina sequencer and could identify both known and unknown viruses.

Originally, a proficiency test to detect viruses in plant material was attempted. Because of the large variability in the results, they were too difficult to compare so a test performance study was completed instead.

Nine labs were given two pools of freeze-dried plant material, and the chemicals needed for total RNA extraction. They were asked to send the extracted RNA to a designated HTS provider, then both analyse the results themselves using in-house bioinformatics protocols and send the raw data to the German partner (JKI) to analyse using VirTool. Of the 8 labs that responded, 4 identified all viruses in pool 1 and 3 identified all viruses in pool 2. Only one false positive was found: an avian coronavirus. The largest deviation was for a virus which did not have a sequence in GenBank at the time of the test. VirTool performed well in the test by identifying all the viruses in each of the tools. Bioinformatics expertise is important to get a full picture of viruses present in a sample when analysing results.

Sequences from new plant viruses or virus variants identified during this project were deposited into public databases such as GenBank and any quarantine viruses to the EPPO Q-Bank.

This project has provided foundational information for drafting guidelines on the validation and verification of HTS workflows which will contribute to a harmonized tool to identify viruses and viroids in plants.

6.6 Northern Europe

One thousand eleven (1011) samples collected from 13 plant nurseries across six countries (FR, GB, GR, IE, IT, US) were collected. This included 647 root samples and 364 water samples, with 627 samples analysed by baiting and 384 samples analysed by metabarcoding.

A high diversity of *Phytophthora* (65 known *Phytophthora* species including quarantine-regulated species and some first country records) was detected across the 13 sampled nurseries. *Phytophthora* was found in the irrigation water at several of the nurseries highlighting water management as a key priority area for improvement. High risk hosts with consistent *Phytophthora* associations included *Fagus*, *Ligustrum*, *Thuja*, *Lavandula*, *Quercus* and *Choisya* spp. Other nursery risk factors which increased the likelihood of *Phytophthora*-positive samples included reliance on greater than 50% imported plant stock and growing a high diversity of plant genera. Analyses were also able to identify *Phytophthora* species' sensitivities to substrate (water *versus* root), nursery latitude and detection method (baiting *versus* metabarcoding), which assists understanding of their lifestyle, habit and sensitivity to detection method, facilitating further prediction of risk.

6.7 Pacific Islands

New Zealand indigenous plant species (n=130) comprising 72 genera, growing in the University of California Botanical Garden at Berkeley, California, were screened for *X. fastidiosa*. Multiple PCR-based methods were used to detect the pathogen at the subspecies and ST levels directly from plant material. Nine plant species tested positive by at least two PCR-based methods. All nine infections were identified as *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* ST 6 or 7 by the amplification of seven housekeeping genes. Three strains were cultured *in vitro* and their whole genome sequences were obtained. These strains belonged to three distinct clades within subspecies *multiplex*, indicating that the infections were not transmitted among these New Zealand indigenous plant species (Groenteman *et al.*, 2015; Vinovsky *et al.*, 2024). Similar research is planned to examine additional key plant pathogens found in the Pacific region.

6.8 South-East Asia

Current assessments reveal that while several countries in South and Southeast Asia possess basic diagnostic facilities, there is significant disparity in terms of technical expertise, diagnostic infrastructure and standardized practices. This variability impedes the early detection and identification of quarantine pests, resulting in delayed responses and potential trade disruptions.

Key examples where diagnostic challenges are evident (CABI, 2022) include:

- Insects: fruit flies (*Bactrocera dorsalis*) are major quarantine pests impacting regional fruit trade. While institutions like the National Bureau of Agricultural Insect Resources (NBAIR), India, possess strong expertise in insect diagnostics, many countries lack specialized entomological diagnostic laboratories with the capability for molecular and morphological identification
- Bacteria: bacterial wilt (*Ralstonia solanacearum*) severely affects solanaceous crops (e.g., tomato, potato). Accurate detection requires advanced bacteriology laboratories equipped for pathogen isolation and molecular confirmation, which remain limited in several national systems. Citrus canker, caused by the bacterium *Xanthomonas citri* subsp. *citri*, is widespread throughout the region and poses a biosecurity threat to global citrus industries. Molecular diagnostic techniques are required to detect the bacterium in asymptomatic plant tissue

- Viruses: the spread of banana bunchy top virus (BBTV) exemplifies the need for early viral diagnostics. However, many laboratories lack facilities for nucleic acid-based detection (PCR, RT-PCR) critical for rapid virus identification
- Fungi: Fusarium wilt, especially *Foc* TR4 affecting bananas, highlights gaps in fungal diagnostics, requiring specialized culture, pathogenicity testing and molecular tools that are often missing in national labs. Anthracnose and stem die-back caused by complexes of *Colletotrichum* spp. are difficult to detect and identify without species-specific PCR technology (Wang *et al.*, 2021)
- Nematodes: root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are a major hidden threat to many crops, yet nematode diagnostic expertise and facilities are particularly scarce across the region, hindering routine surveillance

Preliminary findings from regional cooperation efforts, such as those under ASEAN frameworks, have illustrated the potential for harmonized plant health measures but also emphasized the lack of a formal, structured regional diagnostic system (ASEAN, 2021). Critical issues identified include:

- Infrastructure gaps: most national laboratories require upgrading with modern diagnostic equipment, such as real-time PCR systems, sequencing facilities, insect rearing chambers and nematode extraction units
- Capacity limitations: There is a shortage of trained diagnosticians capable of dealing with a wide array of pest groups, from microscopic nematodes to complex viral pathogens
- Lack of standardized protocols: varying diagnostic approaches across countries undermine the credibility and acceptance of pest detection results
- Delayed information sharing: without a structured network, diagnostic findings are not efficiently shared across borders, delaying coordinated regional responses

Building a Regional Diagnostic Laboratory Network (RDLN), with a central reference centre and country-level satellite laboratories, would address these critical gaps. Leveraging centres of excellence like NBAIR for specific pest groups (e.g., insects affecting fruits) would ensure that technical leadership and mentorship are available within the region, fostering a resilient and harmonized diagnostic capacity essential for safe agricultural trade.

6.9 Southern Europe and Mediterranean

The Ethephon-based method was tested to stimulate the appearance of CBS symptoms on citrus asymptomatic fruits from positive CBS orchards. The experimental assay was conducted according to the protocol of Baldassari *et al.* (2007).

In countries where the pathogen is present, e.g. Brazil and Tunisia:

- The Ethephon-based method accelerated ripening of asymptomatic *C. limon* fruits and was effective to develop early CBS symptoms
- The time of fruit immersion in Ethephon solution is cultivar-dependent
- The most effective dose of Ethephon solution is cultivar-dependent too
- The minimum time of incubation for ethephon-treated fruits to develop CBS symptoms was 2 weeks

In countries where the pathogen is not present, e.g. Greece and Italy:

- No CBS symptoms were developed on ethephon treated fruits
- Some of the treated fruits exhibited rind breakdown because of the long incubation period (35 days)

7. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS

7.1 Africa

PoC diagnostic assays for ToBRFV will provide for a portable, rapid and user-friendly testing methods that will support the detection of the virus outside of laboratory settings, such as in greenhouses, fields, nurseries or border inspection posts where imported seeds and planting materials are imported through. These tools are essential for early detection, containment and reducing virus spread, especially in resource-limited or high-risk environments, and will support reduction of diagnosis costs during surveys to establish ToBRFV a requirement for export of potential hosts of the virus.

7.2 Australia

The protocol for *X. fastidiosa* was submitted to the Subcommittee for Plant Health Diagnostics (SPHD) and endorsed as the national standard. The protocol was broadened to encompass primary detection, diagnosis and surveillance of all *X. fastidiosa* species, subspecies and sequence types across a broad range of hosts.

7.3 Central Asia

In order to effectively manage cotton bollworm, it is recommended to use *Trichogramma chilonis* at a rate of 1 gram per hectare, 3 times per generation. The use of 1000 ectoparasites per hectare in the morning or evening can result in good pest management.

7.4 Latin America and the Caribbean

To address the diagnostic gap in Latin America and the Caribbean, it is recommended to support the development of shared regional laboratories and mobile diagnostic units, and to promote the adoption of harmonised pest detection protocols. These measures would allow faster and more reliable identification of quarantine pests, facilitate coordinated responses to cross-border outbreaks and strengthen compliance with international trade requirements. The experience of the regional diagnostic network for HLB shows that a collaborative approach-based on shared methodologies, capacity building and cross-border surveillance-can enhance plant health governance across the region. Expanding this model to other priority pests would improve preparedness and help safeguard agricultural production, rural livelihoods and regional trade.

7.5 North America

HTS is a tool that can be used to identify viruses and viroids in samples where conventional methods have failed to determine the pathogen causing disease. Furthermore, HTS can reduce the time needed to screen large numbers of plants that may be required as part of import or export testing.

While widespread implementation of HTS currently faces certain constraints (e.g. costs per sample may influence when to use HTS, variation in results may be observed due to technical parameters such as sample preparation and level of expertise in bioinformatics analysis and the need to harmonize and validate workflows), ongoing research on this technology holds significant promise in mitigating these challenges.

7.6 Northern Europe

Phytophthora-contaminated open water sources appeared to be a major problem for most nurseries tested. It is recommended to highlight the risks of using open water sources and direct resources and to promote the most appropriate water treatment methods for nursery management (Green *et al.*, 2023).

7.7 Pacific Islands

Knowledge gained from this approach can, and is being applied to policy in the following ways:

- New plant species added to plant lists tested in border screening
- Diagnostic methods taken up by the border regulator
- Information used to inform disease risk assessment for novel plant hosts
- Identification of host plant refugia for incursion management in landscape environments

The work illustrates the applied value of diagnostics developed over wide geographical expanses and similar climates (e.g. Pacific Islands) and emphasises the need for funding agencies to support international collaborations to optimise plant health outcomes.

7.8 South-East Asia

Current diagnostic capacities across South and Southeast Asia are uneven and often inadequate for early and accurate identification of these threats. A RDLN, supported by a core reference laboratory and national satellite laboratories, would substantially strengthen the region's ability to detect, diagnose, and respond to biosecurity threats. Establishing such a network would enhance early warning systems, facilitate compliance with international phytosanitary standards and improve regional and international market access for agricultural products (FAO/IPPC, 2022).

Critically, investment in modern diagnostic infrastructure, training of specialized diagnosticians and harmonization of diagnostic protocols across countries are urgently needed. Leveraging existing centres of excellence such as NBAIR for insect pests diagnosis, particularly those affecting fruits, would further strengthen regional capabilities (ICAR-NBAIR).

It is proposed that the APAARI take the lead in implementing and coordinating the RDLN if the project is approved. Furthermore, key regional organizations such as the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) may be engaged in dialogue and collaboration to ensure broad-based regional support and alignment. The Australian Crawford Fund may support APAARI to deliver capacity building through masterclasses delivered in the region. Through a concerted regional effort led by APAARI, and with strategic involvement of SAARC and ASEAN stakeholders, the RDLN can serve as a transformative platform for advancing agricultural biosecurity and promoting safe, sustainable trade across South and Southeast Asia.

7.9 Southern Europe and Mediterranean

Ethephon treatment can be useful in infested countries for orchards investigations to anticipate maturation and appearance of symptoms but not for border inspections of imported citrus fruit in countries where the pathogen is not present because it is time-consuming and not effective on already-ripe fruits (Aragona *et al.*, 2024).

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